

An Object Space for Secure and Sovereign Sharing of Reusable Code Objects

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Abstract. This paper introduces the ENACT Object Space, a novel framework for secure, interoperable, and policy-compliant sharing of reusable code objects, such as executable scripts, configuration files and deployment templates. Departing from the traditional Data Space paradigm, the proposed Object Space extends the principles of secure and sovereign sharing from data to software artifacts, enabling developers to efficiently discover, exchange, and reuse code across organizational boundaries. The Object Space reduces duplication of effort, supports policy-driven object sharing and promotes reproducible development practices. To demonstrate this, a proof-of-concept is provided that showcases how shared code artifacts can be retrieved and reused through the ENACT Software Development Kit during application development and deployment within the ENACT continuum. By providing curated, ready-to-use assets, governed by explicit usage policies, the Object Space accelerates development processes, enhances interoperability, strengthens collaboration among participants, and ensures that organizations maintain full control and governance over their shared software artifacts.

Keywords: Data Spaces, Interoperability, Sovereignty, Governance, Application Development

1 Introduction

The rapid evolution of edge-to-cloud computing paradigms has led to increasingly complex distributed applications that span across diverse heterogeneous infrastructures. These applications rely on the ability to acquire, circulate and use data seamlessly

across their operational ecosystem, removing any organizational silos, while ensuring data sovereignty, interoperability, and trust. Therefore, they demand specialized mechanisms that enable secure collaboration beyond enterprise and technological boundaries. In this context, Data Spaces have emerged as a key enabler for sovereign data sharing among multiple data stakeholders. Being a central concept in the European Data Strategy [1], Data Spaces aim to establish a federated ecosystem in which data can be moved and used freely yet responsibly, under clearly defined governance, usage, and access rules.

Despite their increasing adoption, current Data Space implementations primarily target the exchange of consumable data. However, modern distributed applications often demand more than data sharing alone. Distributed computing environments increasingly need to exchange and reuse code objects, such as executable scripts, configuration files or deployment templates, that encapsulate programmable logic for application development and deployment. Sharing such code artifacts can substantially accelerate application development, automate deployment in distributed environments, promote reproducibility, and foster collaborative innovation. Yet, no existing Data Space framework currently supports the sharing of usable code objects in a standardized and interoperable manner.

This paper addresses this gap by introducing an innovative Object Space, extending the conventional Data Space model to support the sharing of reusable software artifacts. The proposed Space acts as a single code marketplace which offers to participants the ability to contribute, discover, access and reuse executable code objects securely. In this way, the Object Space extends the data economy principle of Data Spaces to the software domain, fostering an open and sovereign ecosystem for code sharing and reuse across enterprises and sectors. This approach empowers developers to build distributed applications more efficiently as it enables knowledge transfer among them, thus reducing the duplication of effort and promoting the use of common development practices. This Object Space has been designed and implemented in the context of the ENACT project [2,3].

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews existing initiatives and related work in the field of Data Spaces and distributed object sharing. Section 3 presents the architecture and implementation of the proposed Object Space. Section 4 presents a proof-of-concept scenario showcasing the potential of the Object Space to support application development and deployment, and Section 5 concludes the paper with final remarks and directions for future work.

2 Relation to existing initiatives & work

Data Spaces are emerging as a key paradigm for secure, sovereign, and interoperable data sharing across organizations and sectors. They enable participating entities to exchange data while ensuring that data providers retain ownership and full control over their assets. The European Union has been actively promoting the development of Common European Data Spaces [4] through initiatives such as the European Data Strategy [1], which envisions building a federated data ecosystem wherein data flows under

clearly defined rules on who can use the data, under what conditions, and for which purposes. Currently, this effort is being supported by developing Common European Data Spaces for facilitating data pooling, access and sharing in 14 key strategic EU sectors, including the AgriDataSpace [5] for agricultural data, the Mobility Data Space [6] and PrepDSpace4Mobility [7] for logistics and mobility data, and Data Space 4.0 [8] for industrial data, to name a few.

In that regard, it is of major importance to ensure compatibility with the standards, guidelines and reference architectures established by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) [9] and Gaia-X [10] initiatives. In this context, the IoT-Connector [11] allows for the sharing of IoT sensor data with IDS-based Data Spaces, leveraging the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) SensorThings API to enable interoperability between vendor-agnostic IoT devices and IDS infrastructures. Furthermore, the Simpl middleware platform [12] provides secure data access and interoperability across European Data Spaces.

While conventional Data Spaces focus on datasets, distributed applications increasingly require mechanisms for sharing code objects as well, i.e., ready-to-use software artifacts like code snippets. Unlike static data, code objects can be retrieved, customized, and executed by developers, enabling greater modularity and reusability in application development. However, as of today, this concept has been addressed only partially. Relevant approaches include BSC dataClay [13] and Capybara [14]. dataClay is an object-oriented distributed store allowing third parties to share objects using personalized interfaces, as if those objects were stored locally. Capybara, on the other hand, is a scalable, programmable distributed object store tailored to edge settings, enabling the sharing of serverless function objects. Nonetheless, despite their innovations, both dataClay and Capybara lack compatibility with broader Data Space ecosystems, thus facing interoperability constraints.

Motivated by the above, we introduce a novel Data Space designed to enable policy-compliant and distributed sharing of code objects including scripts, functions, and deployment files. Shared code objects are made available to other developers and can be re-used as templates to speed up application development. By enabling object sharing, the proposed Data Space not only accelerates the application development process but also fosters collaboration and sovereign knowledge transfer among developers. Such capabilities are particularly relevant in modern cognitive and autonomic edge-to-cloud environments, where portability and composability are essential.

3 Object Space Setup

3.1 Overview

Our approach focuses on extending the Data Space core concepts [15] to enable the secure exchange of executable software artifacts while preserving compatibility with established standards and protocols. To achieve this, we designed an Object Space that adheres to the principles set out by the IDS reference architecture model [16], which provides the functional specifications required for implementing Data Spaces. According to the IDS model, a Data Space comprises the

participants acting as asset providers and/or asset consumers, the intermediaries which offer trusted services like metadata management and key components such as connectors, identity providers, etc. Among these, Data Space Connectors constitute the core component. They serve as the gateway for participants to connect to a Data Space, enabling the data sharing between data providers and data consumers. A provider acts as the source endpoint, offering assets or services while retaining ownership and control over how and by whom the data is accessed. The consumer can discover and consume these assets based on the agreed-upon contracts and usage policies. Data Space Connectors provide the mechanisms for secure data discovery, sharing and transfer, automating contract negotiations on data usage and facilitating the enforcement of access and data governance policies.

Building upon this design, the proposed Object Space extends typical Data Space-based data-sharing to support the controlled exchange of code objects, including executable scripts, deployment templates, and configuration files. It involves two main actors: the providers who expose code objects for sharing and enforce the usage policies, and the consumers which discover, negotiate and retrieve code objects. This distinction enables clear role separation and supports scenarios where a single entity may act as both provider and consumer at the same time for different code artifacts.

The developed Object Space offers the following capabilities:

- Federated identity management, enabling participants to register and authenticate themselves through trusted identity providers.
- Policy-driven access control with fine-grained usage control policies to govern data usage and code execution.
- Semantic object cataloging and discovery, allowing participants to publish and search for code objects across organizational boundaries.
- Automated asset transfer workflows compatible with various technologies for distributed storage.

3.2 Connectors Implementation

Our implementation leverages the soviety Community Edition Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) connectors [17]. The soviety connectors are built upon the EDC Connectors [1818], which are fully compliant with IDS and Gaia-X specifications. They ensure secure communication between participants, expressing and enforcing usage control rules through Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL), and support identity management via bespoke centralized IDS identity authorities through the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS). They also provides interoperability with other dataspace technologies and facilitates participants to join existing dataspace via the “Connector-as-a-Service” enterprise-grade managed service.

In our Object Space, multiple soviety connectors were deployed and configured to represent distinct organizational entities, being assigned with the two main roles, i.e., providers and consumers. Each connector maintains its own asset catalog containing metadata about available code objects, including descriptions, versioning information, etc. The sharing of code assets is achieved following the stepwise process illustrated in

Fig. 1. As shown, the connectors intercommunicate via their dataspace protocol API endpoints exchanging messages for catalog queries, contract offers, negotiation responses, and data transfer requests. Furthermore, users can interact with the connectors either through the management API endpoint or via the built-in sovrity EDC User Interface (UI), which is integrated with the connectors by default, thus facilitating manual management and monitoring.

Fig. 1. Asset sharing workflow in sovrity connectors

The exact workflow for offering and consuming assets is as follows:

1. *On provider side:*

- a. *Asset creation:* The provider defines a new code object asset, including its metadata (name, version, description) and object source, i.e., API endpoint from which the connector can retrieve the actual asset.
- b. *Policy creation:* Access and contract policies must be defined. Access policies determine the conditions under which a code object offer is visible to other Object Space participants, while contract policies specify the conditions under which the assets can be consumed.
- c. *Contract definition:* A contract is defined for each offer, binding assets to relevant policies. Once the contract is created, it is published as an offer in the provider's catalog, making it discoverable to Object Space participants deemed eligible according to the access policy.

2. *On consumer side:*

- a. *Catalog browsing:* Eligible consumers can discover and view available offers by querying their catalog browser, which lists all offers visible under the current access policy.
- b. *Contract Negotiation:* It automatically establishes an agreement between providers and consumers. Consumers can negotiate the offer, declaring that they consent to the defined usage conditions.
- c. *Asset Transfer:* Upon successful negotiation, the consumer initiates the transfer of the actual object. The consumer is prompted to provide an endpoint pointing to its object sink. After initiating the transfer, it will be automatically verified that a valid contract exists and the corresponding policies are satisfied; if so, the asset will be transferred from the object source to the client's object sink.

Regarding object storage, the connectors have been integrated with MinIO [1918], a high-performance, S3-compatible, multi-tenant object storage system. MinIO enables efficient management of unstructured data such as code artifacts and binaries. It automatically organizes and stores assets with rich metadata including transfer timestamps, source connector information, and data provenance tracking, while also providing isolation by creating dedicated storage buckets per dataset. This makes it well-suited for collaborative and distributed development environments.

To facilitate developer interaction with the Object Space, we developed a RESTful API using Node.js¹. The API serves as the primary programmatic interface through which developers and applications interact with the EDC connectors, abstracting the complexity of low-level dataspace protocols and exposing high-level operations for code object lifecycle management. This API provides endpoints supporting the complete code object sharing workflow, starting from token acquisition from soivity DAPS and participant registration, to publishing code objects offers, catalog querying and automated contract negotiation and object transfer. In addition, the deployed soivity connectors interface with MinIO through this API, ensuring interoperability and allowing for migration to other S3-compatible storage backends.

For identity and access management, we rely on the soivity DAPS [20], which is premised upon the Keycloak IAM service [21], extending it with custom protocol mappers that generate Dynamic Attribute Tokens (DAT). In practice, soivity DAPS serves as the central identity provider, issuing OAuth 2.0 tokens that authenticate participants and authorize them to access and share code objects within the Object Space. For our implementation, a dedicated DAPS realm² was created with relevant client scopes determining the set of attributes to be assigned upon participant registration. Both provider and consumer connectors were registered in this realm and assigned their respective roles. Once registered, connectors acquire DATs which are then used during communication to automatically authenticate themselves.

The high-level view of the Object Space is depicted in **Fig. 2**.

4 Proof of concept

The Object Space has been integrated with the ENACT Software Development Kit (SDK) [22], a toolset of Python and Java-based components designed to facilitate application development and deployment across the edge-cloud continuum. The SDK provides a user-friendly interface that assists developers in automatically coding and customizing deployment artifacts. The SDK features a dataspace interface which is directly connected with a soivity connector endpoint used to discover offers, negotiate contracts, and transfer assets. The Object Space exposes a variety of artifacts, including manifest files, deployment configuration files, and other, which serve as reusable templates for application deployment. Therefore, through this integration, the deployment process is automated: developers can retrieve off-the-shelf templates directly through

¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/data-access-and-sharing-interfaces/-/tree/enact-api-connector>

² A realm is essentially an independent set of users, credentials, roles and groups, functioning as a tenant for our dataspace participants.

the SDK and configure them as needed, enabling secure, reproducible, and policy-compliant deployment workflows across distributed environments.

Fig. 2. Object Space Overview

Our proof-of-concept scenario involves a developer working on a sample streaming application. Its goal is to create a manifest file for its application that bundles the necessary source files and includes all configurations required for deployment. In addition, the developer desires to deploy its application in the ENACT Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) in order to benefit from ENACT’s deployment and application execution optimization services.

For this scenario, we focus on two representative assets, exposed in the Object Space, depicted in **Fig. 3**: (1) the *sdk-build-manifest.json*, which can be used as the application manifest, and (2) the *kubeconfig-ENACT-cluster.yaml*, a Kubernetes configuration file granting access to a cluster belonging to the ENACT CCC.

Fig. 3. PoC Assets Provided in the Object Space

These assets are published as offers within the ENACT Object Space and can be consumed directly by the SDK. During application development, the developer uses the SDK’s connector interface to discover and retrieve the manifest file (**Fig. 4**). The developer can then configure this manifest within the SDK editor; for example, by specifying container images, runtime parameters, or application dependencies. The

modified manifest is subsequently packaged together with other application source files into a single JAR archive.

Fig. 4. Discovering, Negotiating and Transferring Manifest File

When the developer is ready to deploy its application, it navigates again the Object Space through the SDK and discovers the offer for the kubeconfig file associated with the ENACT cluster. After downloading the configuration locally, the developer imports it into the SDK as the selected deployment profile, as illustrated in **Fig. 5**.

Finally, the SDK automatically builds the application and deploys it in the ENACT CCC. As shown in **Fig. 6**, the deployment is carried out using the edited manifest and is executed on the target cluster specified in the provided kubeconfig.

This PoC demonstrates that ENACT Object Space can effectively support end-to-end application lifecycle activities, by offering templates and code assets for application development, configuration, build and deployment. The integration with the SDK validates the practicality and usability of the Object Space, automating the entire

Fig. 5. Defining the Space-retrieved kubeconfig as the deployment configuration in SDK

workflow. As a result, development is accelerated while also collaboration and sovereign knowledge transfer among participants are promoted.


```

Application Deployment
Streaming deployment status and logs...

Status: Deployment Complete

[16:59:36] Configuration:
  • Deploy Config : kubecfg_enact_cluster
  • Namespace    : default
  • App Name     : test-app
  • Image        : nginx:latest
  • Replicas     : 1
  • ContainerPort : 8080
  • ServiceType  : ClusterIP
  • ServicePort  : 80

[16:59:36] Preparing application for deployment...
[16:59:37] Searching for manifest configuration...
[16:59:38] Manifest configuration found:
  ✓ sdk-build-manifest.json
[16:59:39] Applying deployment settings...
[16:59:40] Settings applied successfully:
  ✓ Namespace: default
  ✓ Replicas: 1
  ✓ Service type: ClusterIP
[16:59:42] Packaging application...
[16:59:42] Application packaged successfully
  ✓ Container image: nginx:latest
  ✓ Package size: 42.3 MB
[16:59:43] Deploying to cluster...
[16:59:45] Deployment resources created:
  ✓ Deployment: test-app
  ✓ Service: test-app-service
  ✓ Pods: 1/1 ready

Elapsed: 9s

```

Fig. 6. Application deployed using retrieved manifest and ENACT kubeconfig

Overall, the ENACT Object Space benefits can be summarized as follows:

- **Reduced Development Time:** The availability of ready-to-use templates lowers significantly the time required to develop code artifacts from scratch.
- **Increased Governance and Trust:** By adhering to Data Space principles, providers retain control over how their assets are used, while policy compliance is enforced through the underlying governance mechanisms.
- **Enhanced Reliability:** Pre-validated code objects decrease the likelihood of errors during build and deployment.
- **Improved Reproducibility and Interoperability:** Shared assets increase consistency and portability of deployments across distributed settings.
- **Reduced Development Effort for Less Experienced Developers:** Access to ready-to-use artifacts reduces development complexity and the effort required by developers with limited experience.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented the ENACT Object Space and detailed its design, architecture, and implementation. Our solution is built upon sovity connectors for dataspace interoperability, the Keycloak-based sovity DAPS for token-based identity and access management, and is integrated with MinIO to provide S3-compatible object storage for shared artifacts. Furthermore, the provided a proof-of-concept scenario in which a developer uses the ENACT SDK's dataspace interface to discover and retrieve manifest files during the development of its application and its deployment in the ENACT CCC, demonstrates the ENACT Object Space practical applicability.

Its applicability can be expanded beyond the presented scenario to support software ecosystems, including cross-organizational DevOps environments, and edge-to-cloud

federations where controlled artifact reuse is crucial. Tighter integration with automated CI/CD and governance mechanisms is planned in the future.

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